

A Stress Analysis Method using Poincaré Plot and Complex Correlation Measures for Wearable Health Devices

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Abstract: This paper attempts to develop a stress analysis method using short-term heart rate (HR) data obtained with wearable health devices. Evaluation method for stress analysis is very important for disease prevention and health promotion. Wearable health devices, such as smart phones and wristband fitness watches, are capable of measuring HR data using photoplethysmography technologies. In recent years, many new commodity devices have been issued and been used to obtain healthcare information, including HR data, in people's everyday life. However, since HR data of wearable devices are recorded with uneven and relatively long sampling intervals, which are constrained by their hardware issues, it is difficult to apply traditional spectral analysis methods for the HR data. The proposed method evaluates HR data using a non-linear technique, Poincaré plot. As the number of points in a plot is restricted by the limited sampling features of wearable devices, this paper applies two stress analysis indices that are based on complex correlation measures of time-varying characteristics in Poincaré plots. On the other hand, the proposed method can investigate dynamic changes in stress levels of short-term (e.g., one minute) analysis duration. Mental stress induction experiments were conducted with nine subjects to validate the proposed method.

Keywords: Stress analysis; Wearable health devices; Heart rate variability (HRV); Poincaré plot; Complex correlation measure (CCM)

I. INTRODUCTION

Recent advances in the area of wearable health technology has brought low-cost and user-friendly healthcare devices. Commodity hardware has been used in a wearable health context and physical activity levels as well as heart rate information can be easily obtained [1][2][3]. The rapid spreading use of these wearable health devices may lead to big opportunities in both consumer and healthcare markets. It is also expected that remarkable changes would be brought in people's lifestyle. A successful wearable health application must have reliable and dedicated data processing methods and health condition evaluation algorithms, which are developed for wearable devices [1].

Stress has become a serious social problem in many countries. Many people suffer from depression and other chronic mental disorders caused by stress. For this reason, stress level analysis and autonomic nervous system (ANS) function assessment are important examples of applications for public health [4]. So far, various stress recognition and evaluation methods have

been developed in the literature, and physiological signals, such as electrocardiogram (ECG) and electrodermal activity (EDA), generally play important roles in these systems [4][5][6]. Especially, stress may induce fluctuations in beat-to-beat intervals, also known as R-R intervals (RRI), and these data reflecting heart rate variability (HRV) can be derived from ECG recordings. HRV data has been extensively investigated for decades and been widely utilized for stress analysis. Besides, some recent research studies also incorporate cognitive information and behavioral reactions for stress assessment [7].

Traditional HRV stress recognition and assessment methods are developed with features extracted from time domain and frequency domain as well as indices based on some nonlinear transformations. It was found that impact of the sympathetic and parasympathetic modulation on the HRV shows clear characteristics on some frequency bands (or components). Spectral analysis of RRI data is a widely-accepted technique, where power amplitudes of two or three frequency bands are evaluated. Low frequency (LF: 0.04-0.15 Hz)

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and high frequency (HF: 0.15-0.4 Hz) components in HRV data are major indices for analysis of ANS activities. The former reflects sympathetic control and vagal modulation, while the latter is considered relating to parasympathetic control [5]. Considering frequency contents in the LF band, a sound spectral estimation requires a relative long term of RRI data, say more than two minutes. In order to obtain changes in stress levels a sliding window is usually used [8][9]. Although time-frequency methods, such as Wavelet transform, have also found their places in the field of stress analysis, relative long term of RRI data is still necessary [10][11][12]. For this reason, it is difficult yet to investigate instantaneous fluctuations and dynamic changes in stress levels and the ANS with features and indices obtained from frequency domain.

Issues related to stress are usually prolonged and recurring and lead complicated damage and disruption in people's everyday life. Stress analysis study needs to extend its steps into monitoring dynamic changes in stress and ANS activities, especially in everyday life situations. The recent trend indicates that focus of research studies has shifted towards evaluation of dynamic changes in stress levels and the balance of ANS activities based on short-term HRV data [13][14]. Here, *short-term* stands for data durations no longer than two minutes, and analysis using HRV data less than 60 s is much more preferred. Some studies have discussed very short-term HRV analysis based on data less than or around 30 s [13][15][16]. On the other hand, dynamic changes of stress levels have much more complicated characteristics in everyday life than those steady conditions studied in laboratory and research environments. This imposes the requirement for HRV data measurement with wearable devices.

Given such a background, the rapid progress of wearable health devices provides valuable instruments for heart rate (HR) acquisition. With the leveraging of miniaturized optical pulse sensors, wearable devices are capable of measuring pulse rate (PR) using photoplethysmography (PPG) techniques [17][18]. Research studies have reported on wristband type fitness devices as a surrogation of traditional HR acquisition equipments. However, these studies do not go further than validation research on the measurement accuracy of these wearable devices comparing with traditional ECG records [3][19][20].

As for HR data measured with wearable devices, it needs to be mentioned that these devices do not possess comparable functionality and characteristics as bio-

signal instruments of research grade. Since wearable devices are limited by issues such as storage space, battery power, and CPU speed, the sampled data usually don't have uniform intervals, and the sampling intervals are larger than traditional instruments used in clinical and laboratory settings. For example, HR data were measured with recording intervals in the range of 5 to 15 s, and gaps in data were also reported [21]. So that traditional HRV analysis methods, especially those from frequency domain, cannot be simply applied.

The present paper attempts to develop an evaluation method for stress level and ANS function based on short-term HR data measured with wearable health devices, such as Fitbit Charge HR and Apple Watch. Autonomic response induced by mental stress is studied and the HR data are measured with a sampling configuration similar to wearable devices. The HR data are evaluated using Poincaré plot in order to deal with the sampling problem, since this method does not have a strict requirement on sampling features.

Poincaré plot is a popular nonlinear HRV analysis method. Most of the traditional Poincaré indices are associated with statistical measures of points in a Poincaré plot [22]. For example, traditional Poincaré-based HRV analysis methods approximate the points in a plot to an ellipse and evaluation indices, such as the ellipse area, are used to represent features of a point cloud. Many traditional Poincaré indices can find their counterparts in indices from time and frequency domains [23][24]. It has been proven that the number of points in one plot largely influences these indices. Since number of points in a plot is small for short durations of data, time-varying features between points has been utilized as analysis indices [25][26][27]. The complex correlation measure (CCM), proposed by Karmaker et al. [25], is considered as the evaluation index in this study. In order to verify the proposed short-term stress analysis method, mental arithmetic experiments have been conducted with nine subjects.

II. METHODOLOGY

Heart rate data can be obtained in the form of beats per minute (BPM) using wearable devices and intervals between samples are several seconds. An averaged estimation of heart rate intervals (HRIs) can be derived as

$$HRI_n = \frac{60}{HR(n)} \text{ [s]} \quad (1)$$

Fig. 1 An example of Poincaré plot with 30 points, which corresponds to HRI data of two minutes.

where $HR(n)$ stands for the n th data in HR series. The HRIs are then processed with Poincaré plot and CCM indices are derived for evaluation of stress levels.

A. Poincaré plot for HRIs

A lag-1 Poincaré plot of HRIs reveals correlation between consecutive samples in the HRI series. The Poincaré plot is constructed with HRI_n on the horizontal axis and HRI_{n+1} on the vertical axis. Here, the subscripts indicate the order of data in HRI series. Points in a Poincaré plot form a representative cloud and both its shape and size of the point cloud can be assessed numerically [22]. Typical measures of Poincaré plot are derived with ellipse fitting on the point cloud. Three traditional indices are defined as the minor axis of the ellipse (SD_1), the major axis of the ellipse (SD_2), and the ratio of SD_2/SD_1 .

Figure 1 shows an example of HRI Poincaré plot for two-minute data. The sampling intervals of these data are 4 s and there are 30 points in the plot. Since the number of points is quite small, traditional ellipse fitting technique based on statistical measures of points cannot provide representative indices. This paper utilizes relationships between points to investigate time-varying features of Poincaré plot for short-term HRV stress analysis.

B. Stress analysis indices using CCM

Complex correlation measure (CCM) is considered as a Poincaré plot descriptor to represent time-varying features. The CCM descriptor is based on area of triangles, which are composed of three consecutive points in a time series, and CCM evaluates point-to-point variation of the time series rather than its statistical and gross measures [22][25].

In a Poincaré plot, as shown in Fig. 2, the $(i-1)$ th triangle is composed of points $P_{i-1}(HRI_{i-1}, HRI_i)$,

Fig. 2 CCM for a 15-point Poincaré plot. The number beside each point stands for its order in the plot.

$P_i(HRI_i, HRI_{i+1})$, and $P_{i+1}(HRI_{i+1}, HRI_{i+2})$. It is obvious that areas of these triangles are functions of HRI data. Mark the area of the i th triangle as $S(i)$, CCM for the Poincaré plot can be calculated as follows,

$$CCM_m = \frac{1}{C_m(N-2)} \sum_{i=1}^{N-2} |S(i)| \quad (2)$$

$$S(i) = \frac{1}{2} \begin{vmatrix} HRI_i & HRI_{i+1} & 1 \\ HRI_{i+1} & HRI_{i+2} & 1 \\ HRI_{i+2} & HRI_{i+3} & 1 \end{vmatrix} \quad (3)$$

where the subscript m stands for the m th evaluation window along the time series, N is the number of points in a plot, and C_m stands for the area of the fitted ellipse.

Since the area of ellipse C_m in the denominator may become a biased estimation due to small size of points, a modified CCM term is proposed as follow,

$$CCM'_m = \frac{1}{N-2} \sum_{i=1}^{N-2} |S(i)| \quad (4)$$

The indices, CCM_m and CCM'_m , are investigated with HRI data obtained in the experiments. In this paper, the data length for each evaluation window is set as one minute.

C. Traditional HRV analysis with RRI data

For reference information on the stress levels, traditional HRV measures are obtained with long-term (five minutes) RRIs derived from ECG signals. The spectral amplitudes of LF and HF components, as well as the ratio of LF/HF are evaluated with an HRV analysis toolkit [28].

Lag-5 Poincaré analysis is also applied with RRI data, which shows cloud of RRI pairs as RRI_n and RRI_{n+5} . Since the RRI data vary in the range of [0.6, 0.9] s the lag-5 plots are not exact counterparts of plots for HRI with 4 s sampling interval, but they can be

Fig. 3 Test sessions in the experiments: Relaxation and stress induction with mental arithmetic.

treated as a close estimation obtained with RRI data. Here, the lag-5 Poincaré plots use one-minute duration of RRI data, which contain more than 60 points.

III. EXPERIMENTS

A. Experimental setup

Mental stress experiments were conducted to collect HR data for relaxation and mental stressed situations. Stress was induced with mental arithmetic, which is a popular method for mental stress testing [29]. Nine healthy subjects (six male and three female; age: 19-20) voluntarily participated in the experiments. The subjects had no experience of stress induction test before the experiments, and none of them were taking any medications during the experiment period.

Figure 3 depicts the procedure of stress induction experiments. The procedure was composed of two sessions, namely, a relaxation session and a mental arithmetic session. Each session took more than five minutes. There were breaks of three to five minutes between two sessions. For the relaxation sessions, the subjects were asked not to move their bodies and keep calm and awake. Mental stress was induced with calculation of two-digit addition, subtraction, and multiplication, some examples of the questions can be found in Fig. 3. The questions were provided in the sequence of addition, subtraction, multiplication, subtraction, and addition, one minute for each division. Every question was displayed on the screen for 5 s and the subject was instructed to make the answers as soon as possible.

Instead of commodity wearable health devices, HR data were measured with a bedside SpO₂ monitoring system (Nellcor™ N-BSJ, Covidien) with a sampling interval of 4 s. The SpO₂ sensor was attached to a subject's left index finger. The subject was asked not to move his/her left hand during the experiments. In addition, ECG data were measured with a multi-telemeter system (WEB-9500, Nihon Kohden). The

Fig. 4 Changes of CCM and CCM' indices for Subj. A. The dashed (red) lines are results of CCM' and the solid (black) are for CCM .

electrodes were placed in the lead II manner. The sampling rate of ECG was 500 Hz. RRI data were derived from ECG records and all R peaks in the ECG signals were visually checked in order to remove ectopic beats and artifacts caused by body movements.

During the experiments, HR data and ECG signals were measured simultaneously. The data processing was done offline. Both the correctness of answers and stress analysis results were not fed back to the subjects.

B. Dynamic changes of CCM indices

Figure 4 shows evaluation results of CCM indices using one-minute term HR data (Subject A). The labels R-# and S-# marked on the horizontal axis indicate the #th minute duration in the relaxation and the stress session, respectively. Changes can be recognized in both CCM and CCM' results, however, there were no consistent trends between two indices. For the CCM index, no comprehensive explanation can be made for its minute-to-minute variations corresponding to the stress and relaxation conditions. According to Ref. [30], CCM index is expected to decrease from its baseline level when a subject turns into a stressed condition. Comparing the average levels of the first five minutes relaxation and the stress session, generally CCM levels are higher in relaxation than the stress session. The rough variation of the first five minutes is due to ill-estimation of ellipse areas for each plot.

An opposite change can be recognized in CCM' results. For the first five minutes, CCM' keeps in a relative low level, which indicate the points in a Poincaré plot *shift* with a small step width. On the other hand, in the stress session CCM' values are enhanced from the relaxation level. Also, the variation between the addition, subtraction, and multiplication divisions reflects difficulties of these mathematical operations.

Results of CCM' , CCM , SD_1 , SD_2 , and C_m for the one-minute durations (Subject B) are listed in Table.1. It is clear that all five indices vary without a clear-cut

Table.1 Summary of the Poincaré and CCM indices for one-minute analysis with HR data of subject B.

	CCM' [ms ²]	CCM	SD_1 [ms]	SD_2 [ms]	C_m [ms ²]
R-1	211.0	0.184	9.46	38.5	1.144
R-2	167.7	0.498	10.3	10.4	0.337
R-3	143.0	0.805	8.01	7.05	0.178
R-4	90.6	0.168	8.32	20.6	0.538
R-5	189.7	0.488	7.39	16.7	0.389
S-1	384.9	0.310	10.6	37.4	1.240
S-2	121.1	0.316	6.57	18.6	0.383
S-3	153.0	0.646	4.97	15.2	0.237
S-4	541.0	0.429	10.3	38.9	1.260
S-5	218.3	0.161	8.67	49.8	1.356

trend, especially for CCM . In addition, variations in SD_1 and SD_2 may make the term C_m in the denominator of Eq. (2) abruptly change. This reason makes C_m not suitable for normalization. Because estimation of SD_1 and SD_2 based on small point size, say 15, can be a biased one so that remarkably affect the index of CCM .

Means and standard deviations (SDs) of CCM and CCM' for five evaluation durations of relaxation and stress sessions are listed in Table.2. In this table, the marks ** in the right column mean the evaluation index for mental stress session is significantly ($p < 0.01$) different from the relaxation session and the mark * means difference between indices of two sessions is statistically significant at a level of 0.05. It can be found that p values of CCM' for 2/3 of the subjects are smaller than their counterparts of CCM . This means that indices

Table.2 Means and SDs of CCM' and CCM for subjects.

Subject		Relaxation	Mental Stress	p values
A	CCM'	66.59±37.75	188.4±128.8	0.102
	CCM	0.273±0.174	0.151±0.062	0.177
B	CCM'	160.4±46.51	283.6±176.2	0.197
	CCM	0.429±0.263	0.373±0.180	0.704
C	CCM'	255.3±159.7	646.5±134.7	0.003**
	CCM	0.138±0.053	0.336±0.122	0.010*
D	CCM'	56.49±21.08	208.4±146.9	0.081
	CCM	0.248±0.058	0.293±0.100	0.407
E	CCM'	323.9±189.9	289.9±253.0	0.815
	CCM	0.329±0.199	0.210±0.036	0.255
F	CCM'	123.4±120.5	200.1±53.63	0.230
	CCM	0.264±0.122	0.264±0.155	0.996
G	CCM'	148.7±88.92	141.9±55.35	0.887
	CCM	0.195±0.085	0.229±0.055	0.472
H	CCM'	162.2±92.16	223.6±87.11	0.310
	CCM	0.342±0.070	0.184±0.055	0.004**
I	CCM'	119.1±47.92	184.3±110.0	0.310
	CCM	0.240±0.123	0.245±0.062	0.936

Fig. 5 CCM and the area C_m of subject C estimated with HRI data, dashed (red) lines, and the lag-5 RRI Poincaré analysis, solid (black) lines.

of CCM' between two sessions show large difference so that it is easier to achieve discrimination with CCM' .

C. CCM with lag-5 Poincaré plot of RRI data

CCM index was evaluated with lag-5 Poincaré plot using RRI data. Figure 5.(a) shows the CCM values of each one-minute duration with HRI (dashed lines) and RRI (solid lines) data (Subj. C), respectively. The CCM results, based on lag-5 RRI Poincaré plot, decrease from its baseline (relaxation) for the stress session. This trend is same as those described in Ref. [30]. However, CCM results of HRI data give a totally different pattern.

The areas of fitted ellipses for all one-minute durations are plotted in Fig. 5.(b). There are more than four times of points in RRI Poincaré plot than the HRI plots, so that the estimated areas are supposed to be more reliable. Decrease of CCM (RRI) from relaxation to stress session is partially caused by the increase of C_m , which cannot be recognized in the C_m values for the case of HRI data. It should be noted that CCM' without the area term is free from the ill-estimation problem.

D. Comparison with traditional RRI analysis

The proposed Poincaré indices and SD_2/SD_1 , based on HRI data, were also compared with traditional spectral measures using RRI. Here, all indices, including CCM and CCM' , were derived with five-minute duration data. The results are summarized in Table.3. Up and down arrows marked besides the indices for

Table.3 Comparison of Poincaré indices and spectral measures with five-minute duration data of nine subjects.

	Relaxation						Stress with mental arithmetic					
	CCM' (ms ²)	CCM	SD_2/SD_1	LF (ms ²)	HF (ms ²)	LF/HF	CCM' (ms ²)	CCM	SD_2/SD_1	LF (ms ²)	HF (ms ²)	LF/HF
Subj. A	70.31	0.141	4.682	172	985	0.175	207.13 ↑	0.098 ↓	7.337 ↑	860 ↑	483 ↓	1.781 ↑
Subj. B	158.39	0.210	3.036	1916	162	11.809	272.79 ↑	0.247 ↑	4.839 ↑	687 ↓	152 ↓	4.519 ↓
Subj. C	252.43	0.126	6.907	491	2145	0.229	619.32 ↑	0.251 ↑	4.062 ↓	3520 ↑	1877 ↓	1.875 ↑
Subj. D	58.86	0.102	8.162	142	69	2.077	202.32 ↑	0.197 ↑	5.099 ↓	558 ↑	134 ↑	4.178 ↑
Subj. E	303.05	0.259	3.142	892	569	1.548	271.50 ↓	0.090 ↓	7.195 ↑	668 ↓	310 ↓	2.154 ↑
Subj. F	121.41	0.175	5.026	330	318	1.038	190.56 ↑	0.103 ↓	12.555 ↑	358 ↑	160 ↓	2.243 ↑
Subj. G	153.16	0.166	3.969	569	214	2.651	144.02 ↓	0.175 ↑	5.380 ↑	448 ↓	89 ↓	5.019 ↑
Subj. H	158.58	0.201	4.522	457	499	0.917	211.75 ↑	0.142 ↓	7.076 ↑	692 ↑	125 ↓	5.520 ↑
Subj. I	101.80	0.154	5.135	279	65	4.313	171.71 ↑	0.146 ↓	6.585 ↑	284 ↑	177 ↑	1.609 ↓

stress session represent change of evaluation indices from its baseline (relaxation). It can be found in the literature that stress increases LF/HF ratios and decreases HF. Except for subjects B, D, and F, changes of the values agree well with changes of stress level. On the other hand, CCM' tends to increase for stress induction while CCM is expected to decrease. The term SD_2/SD_1 is considered as a counterpart of LF/HF ratio in Poincaré analysis. Generally, the results of CCM show less consistence among nine subjects than the other four indices. Only indices of five subjects decreased and the variation for subject I was quite small. On the other hand, values of CCM' indices change largely and seven of nine subjects show same trends in their experimental results.

From the results of Table.3, disagreement can also be found among indices of CCM' , SD_2/SD_1 , HF, and LF/HF, on the variation direction of index for subjects. More investigation studies are required in order to look further into the details of changes between stress and baseline conditions. Since increase in the LF/HF ratio indicates a stress condition in a subject, the results of subjects B and I inform that the subjects may not concentrate in the mental stress test and the experimental protocol needs to be modified with more effective stress induction method or the experimental procedure must be revised carefully.

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper proposed a stress analysis method based on complex correlation measures of Poincaré plot using short-term data. The proposed method does not have strict requirements on sampling characteristics of heart rate data, so that it can be applied to stress analysis using HR data measured with wearable health devices.

In addition, time-varying features between points in a plot are utilized and short-term durations of HR data can be analyzed. Beside the CCM index, a modified version of CCM' has been developed in order to deal with small size of data in Poincaré plots. The indices were examined in the experimental studies with nine subjects. Although both CCM and CCM' do not provide obvious and consistent results between stressed condition and its baseline, the index levels of CCM' are much easier for discrimination between two conditions and the variation in the index levels is larger than CCM .

For future studies, experiments with more subjects are required to investigate the proposed method. In addition, the experimental setup and procedures need to be revised for further detailed researches. The author had developed other Poincaré plot index for short-term HR evaluation [27]. Combination with the proposed CCM indices will be examined and reported in the future studies.

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